

A Study on Crisis Management in India

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Abstract: Metamorphosis in technology and contempo progress in convolution of current lifestyle have exacerbated the plausibility of the frequentness of crisis. Perennial parlous, toxic and inflammable nature of chemical products accentuate the momentous of surveying crisis management into specifics and triumph pertinent to reconnoiter its strategies. Crisis management needs diverse proposition commanding dexterity, wealth and allegiance of corporate, government representatives, inter-governmental and non-governmental establishments, etc. A clear-sighted methodology for crisis management is the crying need of the hour and, hence, there should be sincere efforts to manage the problems of crisis. Against this backdrop, this paper discerns the core issues of crisis management that must be esteemed when instituting its entire biennium in an organization. Meticulous exposition has been effected to articulate the manifoldness of the exertions and dexterity craved for managers when concocting crisis management in an organization. It sprouts pragmatic that top management professionals be familiarized with crisis management mechanism. The paper precipitates multiform key gaps of crisis management in India that does covet approached. The paper also appraises few thrusting germane and offers placid recommendations on how the future approaches for the progress of crisis management in India shall take fashion.

Keywords: Crisis, Management, Organization, Strategy, Government.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern organizations are susceptible to crisis. Although organizations sustain crises of capricious degree on a scrupulously regular basis, sporadically, type of organization itself mountingly increases risks or damages fraternized with these crises. India has savored an impressive array of crises since the birth of recorded history. Geo-climate zone in which India is located surrounded by physical, social and economic vulnerabilities living in high risk areas make India one of the most catastrophic-prone countries in the world. Crises like phenomenon cannot be circumvented, but their debilitating crash can be alleviated through efficacious approach. Therefore, top management professionals get fraternized with crisis management practice. This paper shows that an in-depth knowledge and perception of the exercise of crisis management in India will stabilize better in the roles of advisors and counselors to top management.

II. CRISIS MANAGEMENT-CONCEPT

A crisis being escalating process may not be delineated to one area within a common encompass. It may ensnare rapidly and emerge with other crises and its ramifications are elongated (Hart, Heyse, & Boin, 2001). Normally, crisis embraces three essentials: menace, precipitation and instant decision. Coombs and Hollady (2012) epitomize that every crisis is not formented by problem. Organizations must fabricate their own criteria to adjudicate when problem develops into crisis (Zapletalov_a, 2012). An organization practicing crisis management ventures turbulent and unpredictable event that menaces organization, its stakeholders or general public. Crisis management concerns manifold levels of activity like crisis prevention, planning, training, response and restoration. This practice includes anticipating exigency, developing strategies to minimize harm and implementing these strategies when a crisis occurs. A crisis requires stratagem to modulate preordainment and postulates fast decision-making. It develops across the ages as a small problem exacerbates because organization does not glimpse or emaciate to effectuate debilitation.

III. TYPES OF CRISIS

- **Natural Disaster:** These crises often spring from weather and environmental conditions like storms, droughts, floods and wildfires. Natural crisis is a perturbation in macro environment caused to nature and is usually indomitable.

- **Technological Crisis:** These crises budding from technology issues like hardware problems, software malfunctions, network problems, data loss and computer vandalism. Big interruption can convulse many businesses concomitantly.
- **Confrontation:** This crisis stems from conflict between activists with cause-allied agenda and companies or governments. Incidents embrace boycotts, protests demos and other types of civil disobedience. Confrontation crisis materializes when workers start fighting amongst themselves. They eventually transgress management and give it an reprimand to welcome their essentials.
- **Malevolence:** This type of crisis originates with belligerent or criminal actions against a company and sometimes has the goal of wrecking it like cybercrime, product vandalizing, industrial surveillance, executive ransom, etc. Sordid employees take the succor of criminals and other draconian measures to satisfy their demands.
- **Organizational Misdeeds:** Sometimes management exonerates company's strategies and intercedes like foxiness, ransgress and moves driven by unethical or myopic values that molest stakeholders or important third parties. This elicits crisis known also as crisis of management misdeeds.
- **Workplace Violence:** These crises are attacks by an employee or former employee on other staff members at workplace due to anger related to attacker's employment.
- **Financial Crisis:** A financial crisis can be specific in which a business has an issue like negative cash flow that impairs its potentiality to stand. Companies respond to financial crises with short-term measures such as emergency credit lines and long-term steps e.g. business restructuring, layoffs and other cost-cutting.
- **Personnel Crisis:** These crises are typically ignited by the loss of skeleton staff. Broader personnel crises ensue when staff morale suffers, companies go through periods of impecuniosity and interregnums leave departments inquorate.
- **Victim Crisis:** This category holds crises viewing company as being calamity of eventuality beyond its control like natural disasters, workplace violence and bottomless noise.
- **Accidental Crisis:** In an accidental crisis, the company is imputable but does not deliberately cause the problem. Many product issues position into this type.
- **Intentional Crisis:** These crises booming from resolute actions generate the most bad blood towards organization. Events involving demoralization and dereliction usually fall in this category. Sometimes these crises are avertable because they stem from delusions.

IV. CRISIS MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

- **Devising Solutions Team:** Solutions team is important to get the most constructive team members to address the situation. They should have white authority from management. Management divulges the team and illuminates their enthusiasm in evaluating the predicament.
- **Realities are friends:** The team contemplates eyed on reckoning while fathoming impression on organization. Hunt for the truth with humanity sheds-light-on the mainspring of enigma.
- **Validating the table:** In case of epic crisis, management needs to discharge other obligations from the solutions team for substantiation.
- **Resolving ASAP:** Panic debilitates teams. Rumors demolish credence. Organization's solutions team gets information conceding the leadership team to confiscate the follow-up in concluding the concern.
- **Being Stabilized and Pragmatic:** Organization stalks how a leader behaves to crisis. It is amazingly cardinal to show tenacity and to stay optimistic while these eventualities transpire.
- **Over-disseminating:** Repeated Communication. Flush and Repeat. It may be employees, customers or suppliers-over communication.
- **Possessorship and Participation:** Every leader needs possessorship and participation when key issue arises.
- **Keeping Focused:** Solutions team detects the basic premise of crisis and endorses solutions; everyone needs to keep sharp. All other leaders should be discerning about their duties and focus on success guarantee.
- **Reckoning Solutions Team:** After thriving determination of the creative strategy to subdue the impediment, assessment requires how the team administers crisis and executes strategy for offing auspice.

- **Invigorating Goals:** Solutions team needs to replevy into their schedule so that the contemplation of employees are adroit. Every organization requires to work always on de novo to reach pursuit while reorient intrigues for taming the hindrances.

Novel method to crisis management recipe appraise the internal and external environment (Litovchenko, 2012). Development of salient exigency intrigue should also reckon timesing and deliberations of all stakeholders. These propositions are essence of crisis management semblance and are also followed to different impervious strategies to refute the cavernous pragmatic inquisitions (T_anase,2012).

V. IMPORTANCE OF CRISIS MANAGEMENT

Crisis management succors organizations obviate catastrophes, mitigate unavoidable damages and get operations back to normalcy. Events like the 2020 global pandemic, California's wildfires and other disasters have driven home the earthshaking of vigilance and preparation. Healthy crisis management has competitive advantage. Crises never unfold exactly as anticipated but the planning process develops crisis management skills and a preparedness mindset. Crisis management team must assimilate all calamities befalling their organization that requires both operational staff and top managers. A business continuity plan focuses on keeping operations running. Crisis Management ensnares pursuits facilitating management coupled with workers to eloquently interpret and embrace the events at hand. It also assists individuals to devise strategies to outing of uncertain situations and coherent to metamorphosis in organization. A dedicated solicitation is key to clobbering crisis since it proffers holistic exercise of an adept vista approachable to all parties.

VI. STAGES OF CRISIS MANAGEMENT

Crisis management endeavors precipitate with constituting a team with a leader. They behave through the phases of menace identification, response plans development, plans practice, implementation and the results reviewing. These stages gravitate crucial tasks like detecting warning signs, controlling damage, learning from experience and updating crisis plans. Concocting crisis management plan is the most arduous gig of circumspection. Communication is crux of crisis management.

VII. GOLDEN RULES FOR CRISIS MANAGEMENT

The following crisis management erudition are about universally accredited by experts and lays down rules: i)Grooming crisis dexterity an ongoing process; ii)Staying calm and conveying confidence; iii)Gathering accurate facts; iv)Prioritizing people over property; v)Avoiding making things worse; vi) Communicating clearly and quickly; vii)Appointing one credible spokesperson for consistent messaging; viii)Avoiding fake information; ix)Making sure the crisis team support and resources; x)Recognizing stressed people; xi)Learning from crisis any problem.

VIII. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study is to evaluate the importance of crisis management and the challenges that need to be considered in Indian context.

IX. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section deals with review of crisis management study. Coombs (2007a) classified crisis management literature broadly into three: Corporate Apologia, Impression Management and Image Restoration Theory. Approaches suggest typologies of strategies in post crisis response management. Besides, he divided crisis management literature based on its emphasis: form or content. Research demonstrates to maintain consistency in all outgoing messages during crisis. Traditional research is less rigorous than content research attracting substantially much attention (Coombs, 2007b). Snyder et al. (2006) suggested for sufficient latitude in the classification of crises. They acknowledge the possibility of reclassifying crises from normal to abnormal. Alpsalan and Mitroff (2003a) stated that organizations operating in developing countries stay with high possibility of sabotage and argued that proactive organizations meet disasters by getting designers, operators and maintenance managers of complex systems. Alpaslan and Mitroff (2003b) developed a typology of three types of crises-natural accidents, normal accidents and abnormal accidents based on their review of disasters and plans by varied businesses worldwide. They also conducted crisis management audits in various multinational corporations, government agencies and nongovernmental organizations, and observed organizations awareness to prepare for the crises and defend using

risk management techniques. **Coombs (2007c)** defined crisis as sudden and unexpected event that threatens an organization's operations and poses both finance and reputation. **Coombs (2014)** suggested that managers should focus on timing, victims and addressing misinformation. **Schwarz et al. (2016)** delineated disciplinary foundation for international crisis communication research but omitted to describe media systems or activism while offering broader overview of sociology, psychology, management, economics and anthropology. **Frandsen and Johansen (2017)** dedicated crisis communication across cultures, second on news media and third on social media. Evidence from the world suggests that there are political environments where lobbying is illegal. Activist stakeholders redefine corporation's practices as irresponsible, thereby triggering CSR-based crisis that damages reputational assets (**Coombs & Holladay, 2015**). There is meager literature on crisis communication in India. Most of the work relates to disaster communication (**Dhanesh & Sriramesh, 2016**). **Yodmani and Hollister (2001)** described the emerging role of communication technologies in mitigation, preparedness and recovery phases of crisis management. **Mathew (2005)** highlighted the role of ICTs in disaster management and public health management. **Samarajiva and Waidyanatha (2009)** observed that mobile phones are reliable and affordable solution for alerting last-mile communities even among the poor in developing countries. **Weick (2010)** used a sense making approach to reflect on the Bhopal disaster while **Mukherjee (2011)** based on semi logical analysis of alternative media texts and interviews with activists examined how the rhetoric of advocacy protests about Bhopal gas tragedy. **Allian (2012)** explored the role and extent of citizen journalism in crisis news reporting of the Mumbai attacks. **Narayana and Kapur (2010)** examined the role of mass media especially live television coverage of the Mumbai terror attack and found from a survey that the public felt live coverage of terrorism during the attack showing utter disregard towards public interest. **Murphy (2012)** presented lessons from polio eradication campaigns in few countries including India to tailor campaign messages through home visits, involvement of community leaders and public education, and finally involvement of children in campaigns to help counter campaign fatigue. **Prabhakar and Shaw (2008)** emphasized the magnitude of community based climate change preparedness planning besides the establishment of drought monitoring and early warning systems.

X. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study is descriptive in nature. Descriptive research has been preferred for developing a better profundity of knowledge. Information required for the study has been collected mostly from secondary sources viz. website, books, journals, reports, etc. Besides, the paper being descriptive and conceptual in nature, the opinion expressed in this paper is author's own. The inherent limitation of the study is that as the study is based on published data and information, and this secondary source may be lacking in authenticity, the result inferred therefrom may not be completely dependable. The study takes into consideration the perspective of crisis management and its implementation in India.

XI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

11.1. Crisis Management in India

Crisis destroys hard-earned fruits of painstaking peace-building activities. Thus, puritanism of crisis, afore mere response to its occurrence has been more focus both within India and abroad. India is impuissant in differing levels to abundant natural as well as mock disasters. 58.6% of the landmass is prone to earthquakes of moderate to very high intensity; over 40 million hectares (12% of land) is prone to floods and river erosion; of the 7,516 km long coastline, close to 5,700 km is prone to cyclones and tsunamis; 68% of the cultivable area is vulnerable to drought and hilly areas are at risk from landslides and avalanches. Extreme vulnerabilities involve population growth, urbanization and industrialization, development within hazard zone, ecological damage, global warming, etc. Apropos of human vulnerability, geriatric, women, children-especially women rendered destitute and children orphaned and the paraplegic persons are at risks.

On 23 December, 2005, the Government of India by enacting the Disaster Management Act, 2005 contemplated the design of the National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA) led by the Prime Minister to adopt a holistic approach to disaster management with emphasis on building strategic partnerships at various levels. A typical disaster management continuum comprises several phases; pre-disaster phase like prevention, mitigation and preparedness while post-disaster phase like response, rehabilitation, reconstruction and recovery.

Basic themes of the policy: i) Community based disaster management including final tranche synthesis of the policy, plans and execution; ii)Capacity development in all sweeps; iii)Consolidation of extinct pizzazz and best approach; iv)Cooperation with agencies at global levels; v) Diverse reciprocity.

11.2. Objectives of the National Policy

- Cultivating a culture of obstruction, receptivity and flaccidity in every sphere through knowledge, innovation and education.
- Emboldening extenuation measures based on technology, truism and ecofriend.
- Mainstreaming disaster management into developmental planning process.
- Establishing institutional and techno-legal frameworks to fabricate validating regulatory climate and docility governance.
- Ensuring efficient mechanism for testament, assessment and surveilling of disaster risks.
- Developing synchronous presaging and monition systems with information technology support.
- Boosting productive partnership with media to build perception and contribute towards competencies.
- Ensuring constructive intervention with caring approach towards exigencies of the marginalized group of the humanity.
- Initiating reconstruction as an opportunity to build disaster springy structures and environment for confirming cosy life.

The Act legislates institutional, legal, financial and coordination devices at the national, state, district and local levels to work in close solidarity. The new institutional framework is expected to vaticinate in a transposition from relief-centric approach to positive regime with preeminence on preparedness, prevention and mitigation. NDMA, the highest body for disaster management has the responsibility for making policies, plans and guidelines for disaster management. Central ministries and State Governments elongate due cooperation to NDMA for executing its bidding. National Institute of Disaster Management (NIDM) functions within the framework of copious etiquette and directives enacted by NDMA. National Crisis Management Committee (NCMC) maneuvers other emergencies requiring mercenary involvement of security forces or intelligence agencies.

In conformity with the provisions of the Act, the Central Government takes measures as it deems expedient and coordinates performances of all agencies. The Central Ministries and Departments take into contemplation the recommendations of the State Governments in scheduling various pre-disaster and post-disaster measures for their developmental schemes and projects to effectively respond to disaster situation. It issues directions to central and state governments bodies to assist; these bodies mandatorily honor such directions. The Central Government extends beneficence to state governments and takes measures for the deployment of Armed Forces. The Central Government facilitates coordination with the UN Agencies, international organizations and Governments of foreign countries towards disaster management. Ministry of External Affairs in harmonization with Ministry of Home Affairs (MHA) facilitates external coordination. NCMC encompassing high level officials of the Government headed by the Cabinet Secretary administers major crises. The institutional mechanism at the Centre, State and District levels helps the States manage disasters effectively. The Act mandates the State Governments inter alia to take measures for preparation of disaster management plans, prevention of disasters or mitigation, allocation of funds, establishment of early warning systems, etc. At the district level, District Disaster Management Authorities (DDMA) Act as the district planning, coordinating and implementing body and take measures heeding the guidelines laid by NDMA and State Disaster Management Authorities (SDMA).

Planning Commission appreciates the factors while allocating resources. All Central Ministries and Departments prepare their plans including financial projections to support. Necessary budget is prepared as part of the Five-Year Plans. Besides, civic utilities are constantly monitored honoring worldwide safety benchmarks. The plans incorporate the inputs of all stakeholders for planning.

Nodal agencies recognize digital divide and couch projects for their renovation. Civil Defence also precipitates cognizance through their relevant institutional frameworks. India Disaster Resource Network (IDRN) requires continued growth to include resources of various agencies, domains and disciplines. India Disaster Knowledge Network (IDKN) portal facilitates reciprocity and gassing with appropriate fields of expertise.

Policy proclamation delineates the birth in the novel exodus. It endeavors to encapsulate the strenuous environs that takes a heavy toll of lives and properties, and cripples economic base of communities. Disasters causing setback to economic and developmental growth also seriously influence the national security environment. The central theme believes that disaster intelligent and resilient community will help realize the national vision. This also expresses firm conviction of national leadership to make necessary financial allocations for disaster instead of fruitlessly post-disaster expenditure year after year.

States are increasingly dueled with various unpredictable extremities. In liberal society like India, the new obstacle of profound broadcasting surveillance complicates the maneuvering of crisis situations. It is sagacious, therefore, to have

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institutional mechanisms like crisis management group to react swiftly and efficiently and remain betrothed until tensions taper to sustainable standard. Such mechanisms need well-exercised preparation and ensures incessant assessment and knowledge. Absence of such mechanisms may unfavorably impress germane exigency governance. A comprehensive national security doctrine providing device for full government approach has hitherto been missing in India causing pervasive reliance upon ad hoc means to treat crises.

11.3. Crisis Management Approach

India's crisis management approach is entrenched institutional structure with carefully shaped etiquette and stratagems. Operational drills permit pavlovian responses so that senior security and political leadership can captain major issues. Executing agencies know their respective responsibilities and the scope for ad hoc and sometimes imprudent actions. Detailed meeting records permit methodical evaluation and experience for the future and become the basis for modifying and ameliorating extant practice. However, these practices are occasionally trailed. Arbitrary propositions are quite often the rule as against the exception. Three cases, 2004-Iraq hostage crisis, 2008-Mumbai crisis and 2016-Pathankot attack reveal how Indian policymakers have abandoned to use inveterate crisis management institutional frame. India cozily administered a hostage condition entangling three Indian truck drivers in Iraq in August, 2004 but employed unintelligible and unkempt responses towards two other crises-one gripping a crucial terrorist attack on India's trading capital, Mumbai in November, 2008 and a later attack in January, 2016 on an Indian Air Force base in Pathankot.

11.4. India's Covid-19 Remonstrance

India cinches biowar against an obscure adversary (corona virus). Magnitude of cases and upsurage in the second wave have plunged India into impassable scantiness. Experts adduce much reason for such peregrination including election rallies, scriptural assembly, etc. An aeonian spear in current Covid-19 infections has placed the entire Covid-19 management system in India inofficious. Hence, reappraising existing management responses is sine qua non to ameliorate the environment. Every agency in the country is struggling to negate shortages and cultivate amplitudes; beviies of friendly foreign countries have also transmitted medical devices and substances. Centralized lockdown and management abet India control the spread and precipitate basal competence to decipher the case load during the process of spreading. Predestinately, credit seeking politics pulsate the voice of health being state subject need to federalize together with the problems of migrant labor. Unlocking is essential for sustenance and getting the economy back on path, but prolonging it to bevy for events like elections is gross insouciance. It also brings weakness in reprisal for both governments' waiting for others to take actions and blaming each other for shortages and absurdity. Besides vaccines, a common man, today, is suffering from shortages of oxygen, hospital beds, ventilators and other appliances. Cases of storing of medical supplies, oxygen and hospital beds bespeak percolation and scarcity of crisis management system. Despite increase in national availability, shortages at the stage of common patients raise question marks on efficiency and perspicuity of existing systematization.

With a third string of pandemic on the vista, India must concede it as a dogged proposition and society has to behave consistently. Currently, copious of agencies are sweating for Covid-19 management at national as well as state level without centralized strategic plan with little coordination. The Honorable Supreme Court of India has appointed National Task Force to administer distribution of oxygen and espouses the need for centralized control of slender means. It is imperative to have central agency galvanized with state representatives for collective strategic decision making at strategic level. Pandemic management besides medical care requires sound logistics management.

There is a need to activate NDMA Resource Centre with every possible information on smart boards about patient load, hospital facilities, vaccination, health appliances, aids, etc. to make realistic plans through collective approach. Media outlet needs keeping the nation informed of policy guidelines and allocations as inadequate information leads to rumors, panic and hoarding. Currently Defence Forces, National Cadets Corps (NCC), National Social Service (NSS), Non-Governmental Organization (NGO), etc. are succoring the national efforts to fight against Covid-19 pandemic.

Second upsurage of corona virus has espoused health security as an inextricable part of national security. Struggle needs to be effected with every agency in a coordinated manner to scrape efforts and resources. There needs better coordination to minimize shortages, leakages and improve overall efficiency as rich supplies are required for third wave. Foreign help is welcome but the future demands self-subsistence to defeat the pandemic at a unique speed.

11.5. Exhortations and Rejuvenations

Postmortem analyses implemented apropos the Mumbai and Pathankot attacks evidence several flaws in the state's reaction to the terrorist attacks at both the central and state extents. In both Mumbai and Pathankot, the Indian Government nurtured ad hoc procedures over the established crisis management mechanisms which were either not galvanized or cratered to implement. On close evaluation, the Indian Government's replication to the Mumbai and Pathankot attacks were discursive, maladroit and abortive mainly because it decided to circumvent its own orthodox institutional framework and thwarted to mimic inveterate groove. Deployment of security personnel appears to have been ad hoc, reactive and mostly incohesive. Wholesale devotion to ad hoc responses could not perdure with very precipitately evolving circumstances. There are other blatant violation for which Indian authorities must trail grave amendment principally engrossing personnel, priorities and governance.

Crew. A security is coordinately adroit to its junior-most foot soldier. The best superstructure remains a house built on sand if-not substantiated by quality workforce. Law and order is concerning state subject contrary to national subject. Recruitment is mostly subject to political patronage and corruption. Red tape on heretofore top-heavy system does not seemingly matter unless the reality at the local level is addressed.

Primacies. There is inordinate emphasis on the personal security of political personality and senior officials with no thought for public security. This vivacity elongates enigmatically. Certain political leaders are bastioned by maximum possible security guards at the nation's worth. This is vintage in a democratic society. This dismally sways a nation's virtuosity to clinch public security;

Administration. Over the years, an extensive "arbitrage economy" has germinated in India. The Central Government is slightly maneuvering this problem through transformation of subsidies with explicit transmission of social amenities in the wake of the biometric-based unique identity system known as *Aadhar*. This gumption shrinks arbitrage. However, few tenuousness outlive unaddressed. Legalization and regulation of cross-border trade may proffer important means of mitigating threat. India will keep vulnerable to security challenges without political predilection to venture on crying need innovation.

Let us learn from methodology adversity to administer internal dissection and audit of procedures for demonstrating what done clumsily. In the aftermath of crisis management delinquency, India fudged factual evaluation for its embezzlement indicatively in Mumbai and Pathankot.

11.6. The Kargil Review Committee (KRC) Report

Gobs of the KRC recommendations are justifying revitalizing since they were barely consummated in spirit and subsist to shape crisis management implosion in India. The KRC recommended viz.: Full-time National Security Advisor, Revived Defence Intelligence Agency, Defined Roles for Army, Paramilitaries and Police, Border Management Overhaul, Promoting Important Areas of Study, Improved Information and Media Management, Formulating a Comprehensive Strategy.

An apposite national security planning and decision-making structure for India in the nuclear age is prolonged. An substantive critique of about 75 years demos that the country lithely has been scrimped from varying national security threats without copious vitiation. India can erstwhile stand such ad hoc operation. No follow-up steps have barely enough on this critical recommendation. Ad hocism has pursued to exemplify the nation's reaction to crises even-abiding the birth of model methodology. The Government has prodigality about perception of the means to remedy gaps in security, but these efforts are inhibited by obdurate political impetus and the absence of an overarching and organizing statement of national security strategy. The premier recommendation bowdlerized by the task force belabors the desideratum of a national security doctrine and a national security strategy which capacitate comprehensive, coherent and coordinated policymaking. This strongly reiterates that there dreams an approved template shepherding multiple government agencies to retaliate to novel crises by virtue of a concerted national security doctrine and a strategy.

CONCLUSION

Eloquent crisis management mitigates vandalization and infrequently divulges an organization to appear sturdy than before crisis. No organization is snug from crisis. Meticulous political decisions have debilitated the potency of crisis management in India. Strategies are mostly treasured supporting ad hoc responses dourly enkindling crumby reverberations. An attempt to sway political statement subsequently proves frivolous. Political susceptibility and the desire to be excused for misadventure also throttle luminosity. Penitence of misadventure makes an substantive review of their own gaps and propound metamorphoses for their personal or organizational stake. Both the Kargil Committee and the Task Force on National Security illuminate the exigency for national security doctrine and strategy but

progressive governments have not embraced one although there have been efforts to shoulder the exertion. World is not brooking a crisis in the system but a crisis of the system in which the solid economy has become obstreperous to monetary economy. All solutions must be developed on this crucial reality. Nothing less than a Global Round on a Reconstructed Economic Order is much-needed to maneuver an exhaustive reform and reshaping of the global economy. Ventures of the G20¹ are shrimpy relative to extensive and solemn technique convenient to the scale of the conglomerating crises of the 21st century.

¹ **Footnote:** The G20 is a diplomatic summit constituting most of the world's cripple economies and ventures to explicate burning challenge akin to international monetary balance, global warming sustenance and sustainability.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) Amelioration of the force is crying need. Force on the land and the bullet-proof jackets of the force being shabby adjure revamped.
- 2) Triumphant rambling a crisis desiderates cognizance about maneuvering a crisis before it materializes. **Gonzalez-Herrero and Pratt (1995)** created a four-phase crisis management model process viz. issues management, planning-prevention, crisis and post-crisis.
- 3) Emergency plan should embrace information and instruction for ameliorating key policy to contemplate not only short-term consequences, but also extensive ramifications of every decision.
- 4) An apposite national security planning and decision device for India in the nuclear age is tardy adhering to the revolution in military-tactics and commination of proxy war and terrorism, and the imperious of revitalizing the armed forces.
- 5) Crisis illuminates the need for linguistics on a most eclectic perspective than streaming information.
- 6) Precise proposals of the two important expert groups, the Kargil Committee and the Task Force on National Security clamors instituted as desideratum of a broader national security strategy thereby must be ingrained in national security doctrine.
- 7) National security doctrine must have a 20/20 vision to perpetrate national objectives and likely skepticism and commination for India's divine.
- 8) National security doctrine needs broad political consensus and template for policymaking for government and mainstream society.
- 9) Ad hoc-ism incessantly yields little reception to crises to India's malignant.
- 10) Crisis management cannot but meliorate through ongoing education from past episode. Attempt to ditch transparent accounting trivializes the plausibility of learning insight from authorities appropriating the crises.
- 11) Investigation and accounting must be decriminalized unlike being left to the disposition of political leadership.
- 12) Most crises favors coherent answer from several agencies and may even presuppose entities like media.
- 13) There is impunity to assimilate strategic talent in illuminating the supply chain management during enormity.
- 14) Better symbiosis of assays with civic authorities beseeches to nurture troops in the information and decision-taking circle.
- 15) Defence forces must embolden national endeavors; it is impolitic that a state or district be abdicated to the military for Covid management.
- 16) Allotments through digitized models are imperious to debilitate the Centre-State blame game.
- 17) Security agencies and courts must be coercive in punishing hoarders with accelerated procedure.
- 18) Centralized planning, coordination, virtual allocation of slender resources and decentralized execution at state level are grave need of the hour.

Additional Recommendations: Expeditious feedback, Energetic divulgence, Proper communication mechanism, Philanthropic approach, Concise plan, Tactical squadron, Perceptiveness, Nods messalian workshop, Communication playbook, Well-informed social forum, Integrated approach, etc.

COMMENT

India is progressively accosted with varied fortuitous exigencies. Therefore, it is prudent to have institutional mechanisms to respond adroitly and bide beguiled up-till tensions abate to tame levels. Such mechanisms covet well-prepared practices with designated officials and agencies averring their mandates to validate ongoing monitoring and memorizing. Absence of such mechanisms may abysmally impel felicitous trauma maneuvering. A sweeping national security is rudiment. This has hitherto been unsubstantial in India eventuating capacious credence upon ad hoc means for reckoning crises. India fortuitously maneuvered hostage scoop cocooning three Indian truck drivers in Iraq in August, 2004 but seasoned scrambled and clumsy reciprocation towards two other crises-one major terrorist attack on India's merchandising capital, Mumbai in November, 2008 and thereupon attack in January, 2016 on an Indian Air Force base in Pathankot. We, the Indians are in second crew of Covid-19 ambience. Divinity savvies about the sequential billow. In antiquity, Bhopal Gas Tragedy also substantiates the crisis management declination of India and experiences criticizes from International forum.

FUTURE RESEARCH SCOPE

Several elongations, both methodological and voluminous, are proffered to apprehend amply decision tree during crisis. Further research explicitizes testing generalizability of the present crisis management frame in India. An important extension of this study needs surveying whether crisis types impinge the strategic decision logic. This study is veridical that India has a poor crisis management plan. Once the decision-makers are perceptive to their culpabilities and with how to collaborate during crisis, type of crisis has modest impression. Further, it is hardly possible to be well-prepared for blooming crisis. It, therefore, appears rational to surmise that broad guidelines on managing crisis would accouter the crisis management team to contrive situations and ornaments pragmatic to appraise whether crisis types impress the essence of decision-making in organizations.

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Abbreviations:

- 1. ASAP- As Soon As Possible
- 2. ICT- Information Communication Technology
- 3.CSR- Corporate Social Responsibility
- 4.NDMA- National Disaster Management Authority
- 5.NIDM- National Institute of Disaster Management
- 6.MHA- Ministry of Home Affairs
- 7.NCMC- National Crisis Management Authorities
- 8.DDMA- District Disaster Management Authorities
- 9.SDMA- State Disaster Management Authorities
- 10.IDRN- India Disaster Resource Network
- 11.IDKN- India Disaster Knowledge Network
- 12.NCC- National Cadet Corps
- 13. NSS- National Social Service
- 14.NGO- Non-Governmental Organization
